

THEORETICAL AND NUMERICAL ANALYSIS OF STRESS DISTRIBUTION IN CFRP ROD BOND ANCHOR

A. P Feng¹, B. P Zhang¹*

¹ Department of Civil Engineering, Tsinghua University, Beijing, China

* Corresponding author (zhangpansat@126.com)

Abstract: An elastic shear stress distribution theoretical model is proposed on the CFRP-adhesive interface of single-rod and 7-rods straight pipe bonding anchor. A comparison between theoretical and finite element results reveals the accuracy of the theory which can be used as guidance for preliminary design of the CFRP rod bonding anchor. Bonding anchor using gradient modulus bonding medium is confirmed to have significantly effect on reducing shear force concentration at the loading end by the proposed theory and finite element analysis.

Keywords: *CFRP rod, Stress distribution, Bond anchorage*

1 General Introduction

CFRP rod or cable has advantages of high strength, light weight, excellent fatigue performance and non-corrosive properties, which make it widely used in building and bridge structures. In engineering, anchorage system UU is the key factor of whether CFRP cables can reach tensile strength in service. Compared to steel, the anisotropy and brittleness of CFRP make it more difficult to anchor. Currently, anchorage system can be roughly divided into clamp anchor, bonding anchor and barrel-wedge anchor (Nanni et al. 1996).

CFRP rod bonding anchorage system is mainly made up of metal barrel, CFRP rods and bonding medium between them usually using epoxy resin or cement grout. The surface of CFRP rod can be threaded or sandblasted, and it can also be smooth without any surface treatment. As for the former, anchoring force is mainly provided by chemical bonding, mechanical interlocking and friction on the interface between bonding medium and CFRP rod while mechanical interlocking no more exists on CFRP rod without surface treatment.

In order to generalize the regularities of shear stress distribution on the CFRP-adhesive interface of straight pipe bonding anchor, an elastic theoretical model is proposed and confirmed by finite element analysis. In addition, the idea of bonding anchorage system using gradient modulus adhesives is proved to be possible which can significantly reduce shear stress concentration at the loading end.

2 Literature review

There are already a series of FRP rod anchorage system presented by many scholars. The main design idea is to reduce the radial compressive stress and shear stress concentration at the loading end under tension, and to improve bond-slip relationship between rod and adhesive.

A 4-wedge type anchor used to grip single CFRP rod was proposed (Ezzeldin et al. 1998). Tensile and fatigue properties of the anchor were tested, and the distribution of longitudinal stress, radial stress and shear stress is investigated by FEA method. Many parameter analysis of wedge type anchor have also been done. The effect of friction coefficient, barrel-wedge angle difference and soft metal sleeve on stress distribution and stiffness of the anchor was studied (Campbell et al. 2000). Similar research has shown that friction coefficient, preload value, sleeve material has significantly effect on anchorage performance (Al-Mayah et al. 2001, 2005, 2006). Al-Mayah also mentioned that arc barrel-wedge surface which means dip angle changes in longitudinal direction can reduce stress concentration at the loading end (Al-Mayah et al. 2007).

As for bonding type anchor, a new way to improve anchorage performance is cutting the rod into several pieces along fiber direction at the free end to increase the contact area between rod and adhesive (W.T.JUNG et al. 2011). Bond-slip relationship between FRP rod and cement grout was investigated, the results revealed that surface condition of rod, expansion of cement grout, anchorage length and elastic modulus of the barrel can influence the anchorage performance in different degrees (Benmokrane et al. 2000, Zhang et al. 2002).

There was some research on anchorage of CFRP cables but not as much as single CFRP rod, because it is more difficult to grip a bunch of rods than only one rod. The CFCC strand in Japan already has a mature post-tensioning anchorage system using cementitious based highly expansive material (Tsyoshi et al. 2012), which has been actually used on Penobscot Narrows Cable Stayed Bridge (Rohleder et al. 2008). A new way to anchor CFRP parallel rods is changing elastic modulus of the adhesive along the barrel (Meier.2011). Ceramic particles in different diameters were mixed into resin to change the elastic modulus of the adhesive. The modulus was low to high from the loading end to the free end as shown in Figure 1(Meier.2011), and shear stress concentration was significantly reduced by this method.

Figure 1 Gradient modulus distribution of adhesive

A theoretical model of barrel-wedge type anchor was proposed by Al-Mayah. Stress distribution on the interface and ultimate capacity of the anchor was calculated through preload slippage and displacement coordinate equation using elasticity method. There is also a theory to calculate ultimate capacity of straight pipe bonding anchor (Zhang et al. 2000). The shear stress distribution along the rod was simplified to 3 parts. The bearing capacity of each part can be calculated through integration of shear stress, thus the whole capacity of the anchor can be gained. The error was less than 15% compared to experimental results. Based on the theory above, a simplified model was suggested that each part of the shear stress distribution was considered as a straight line. The ultimate capacity can be gained in the same way (Mei et al. 2007).

3 Theoretical Analysis

This theory can be used to calculate shear stress distribution along single rod or multi rods in straight pipe bonding anchor within elastic stage. The fundamental assumptions are listed as follows.

- (1) All the materials are considered elastic, in other words, the stress state of anchorage system remains elastic in the theory.
- (2) Deformation of the metal barrel will not be considered, since the stiffness of the barrel is much bigger than that of the adhesive. Therefore, the internal surface of the barrel is considered to be fixed.
- (3) Interface slippage is ignored in the theory, so that displacement compatibility can be founded on interface between barrel and adhesive (hereinafter called the first interface) and interface between adhesive and CFRP rod (hereinafter called the second interface).

Thus, the theory is suitable for preliminary shear stress analysis in elastic state.

3.1 Single Rod

The cross section of single rod anchor is shown in Figure 2, and theoretical model of single rod is shown in Figure 3. The length of the anchor is set as l . The diameter of CFRP rod and the radial thickness of adhesive is respectively d and t .

Tensile load with value of T_0 is applied at the loading end of CFRP rod. Assume that the axial displacement of the rod has a uniform distribution in one section which is set as $u(x)$. Axial force distribution is set as $T(x)$. Interfacial shear stress on the first interface and the second interface is $\tau(x)$ and $\tau_b(x)$, while x represents the axial coordinate. The value is 0 at the free end and l at the loading end of the anchor.

Figure 2 Cross section of single rod anchor

Figure 3 Theoretical model of single rod

Figure 4 Stress state of single rod anchor

Figure 4 shows the stress state of CFRP rod and adhesive within infinitesimal length dx in axial direction. For CFRP rod, the equilibrium and geometric equation can be easily gained.

$$\tau(x) = \frac{1}{\pi d} \frac{dT(x)}{dx} \quad (1)$$

$$T(x) = E_c A \frac{du(x)}{dx} \quad (2)$$

E_c is the longitudinal elastic modulus of CFRP rod, and A is the sectional area. For the adhesive, the shear stress on the first and second interface can be approximately considered as equilibrant forces, so we can get

$$\pi d \tau(x) dx = \pi(d+2t) \tau_b(x) dx \quad (3)$$

Assume that the shear strain has a linear distribution in radial direction, thus the average shear strain can be gained with equation (3).

$$\bar{\gamma}(x) = \frac{1}{2G} [\tau(x) + \tau_b(x)] = \frac{d+t}{d+2t} \frac{\tau(x)}{G} \quad (4)$$

G represents for shear modulus of adhesive. The relative displacement between the first and second interface is $u(x)$, therefore, we can get the geometric equation of adhesive with equation (4).

$$\frac{u(x)}{t} = \bar{\gamma}(x) = \frac{d+t}{d+2t} \frac{\tau(x)}{G} \quad (5)$$

With equation (1) (2) (5) and set $u(x)$ as the variable, we can get the differential equation that is satisfied at any infinitesimal point.

$$u''(x) - k^2 u(x) = 0 \quad (6)$$

$$\text{while } k^2 = \frac{d+2t}{d+t} \frac{4G}{E_c dt}$$

The general solution of equation (6) is $u(x) = C_1 e^x + C_2 e^{-x}$. With boundary conditions at the free end $u(x=0)=0$ and the loading end $T(x=l)=T_0$, the value of C_1 and C_2 can be calculated as

$$C_1 = \frac{d+t}{d+2t} \frac{T_0 kt}{\pi G d (e^{kl} + e^{-kl} - 2)}$$

$$C_2 = -\frac{d+t}{d+2t} \frac{T_0 kt}{\pi G d (e^{kl} + e^{-kl} - 2)}$$

Therefore, the shear stress distribution in the above discussed state can be gained.

$$\tau(x) = \frac{d+2t}{d+t} \frac{G}{t} (C_1 e^x + C_2 e^{-x}) \quad (7)$$

However, if the modulus of the adhesive is not constant along the CFRP rod, such as the gradient modulus distribution mentioned above, the boundary conditions will be different. On this occasion, we can divide the anchor into n parts, and the modulus of the adhesive remains constant value G_i at each part. Thus the i^{th} part has the displacement distribution $u_i(x) = C_{1i} e^x + C_{2i} e^{-x}$ with unknown variables C_{1i} and C_{2i} , so that there are totally $2n$ variables need to be solved. Firstly, boundary conditions $u(x=0)=0$ and $T(x=l)=T_0$ still exist at the moment. Secondly, the axial displacement and strain must be continuous on the interface of each part which can be expressed as $u_i(x_i) = u_{i+1}(x_i)$ and $u_i'(x_i) = u_{i+1}'(x_i)$ while i equals from 1 to $n-1$. Together we already have $2n$ boundary conditions and the equations can be solved out. The shear stress distribution at each part can also be expressed as equation (7).

3.2 Seven Rods

The stress distribution in multi rods can also be derived from the theory above proximately. For 7 rods symmetrically anchored, Figure 5 shows the cross section of the anchor. The diameter of the rods is d . The radial thickness of the adhesive between the center rod and the 6 side rods is t_1 while it is t_2 between the 6 side rods and the barrel. Other parameters are the same as single rod anchor in section 2.1.

Figure 5 Cross section of 7 rods anchor

Different from single rod, the shear stress distribution on the surface of 6 side rods is not uniform along the perimeter. To simplify theoretical calculation, the adhesive is regarded as two layers of concentric rings, and shear stress on side rods is divided into inner stress distribution $\tau_{2i}(x)$ and outer stress distribution $\tau_{2o}(x)$. Stress along the center rod is set as $\tau_1(x)$. Axial displacements of center rod and side rods are expressed as $u_1(x)$ and $u_2(x)$, while axial forces are $T_1(x)$ and $T_2(x)$. Stress state of CFRP rod and adhesive within infinitesimal length is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6 Stress state of 7 rods anchor

According to equilibrium and interaction relationship from Figure 6, inner shear stress distribution on side rods has an opposite direction to

others which indicates that the stress state of multi rods anchor is more complicated than single rod one. The equilibrium and geometric equation of center rod and side rods can also be listed.

$$\tau_1(x) = \frac{1}{\pi d} \frac{dT_1(x)}{dx}, T_1(x) = E_c A \frac{du_1(x)}{dx}$$

$$\frac{\tau_{2o}(x) - \tau_{2i}(x)}{2} = \frac{1}{\pi d} \frac{dT_2(x)}{dx}$$

$$T_2(x) = E_c A \frac{du_2(x)}{dx}$$

Through proper simplification we can get

$$E_c A \frac{d^2 u_1(x)}{dx} = \pi d \tau_1(x) \quad (8)$$

$$E_c A \frac{d^2 u_2(x)}{dx} = \frac{\pi d}{2} [\tau_{2o}(x) - \tau_{2i}(x)] \quad (9)$$

For the adhesive, the shear stress on each layer are also approximately considered as equilibrant forces

$$\pi d \tau_1(x) dx = \pi (d + 2t_1) \tau_{2i}(x) dx \quad (10)$$

$$\pi (3d + 2t_1) \tau_{2o}(x) dx = \pi (3d + 2t_1 + 2t_2) \tau_b(x) dx \quad (11)$$

It can be seen from Figure 6 that the relative shear displacement of adhesive layer 1 is $u_1(x) - u_2(x)$, while that of adhesive layer 2 is $u_2(x)$. Use the same method mentioned above, we can get the geometric equation of adhesive with equation (10) (11).

$$G \frac{u_1(x) - u_2(x)}{t_1} = \frac{\tau_1(x) + \tau_{2i}(x)}{2} = \frac{d + t_1}{d + 2t_1} \tau_1(x) \quad (12)$$

$$G \frac{u_2(x)}{t_2} = \frac{\tau_{2o}(x) + \tau_b(x)}{2} = \frac{3d + 2t_1 + t_2}{3d + 2t_1 + 2t_2} \tau_{2o}(x) \quad (13)$$

With equation (8) (9) (10) (12) (13), the displacement $u_1(x)$ and $u_2(x)$ are remained as variables to be solved.

$$\frac{d^2 u_1(x)}{dx^2} = C_1 u_1(x) - C_1 u_2(x) \quad (14)$$

$$\frac{d^2 u_2(x)}{dx^2} = C_2 u_1(x) + C_3 u_2(x) \quad (15)$$

$$\text{While } C_1 = \frac{4G}{E_c d t_1} \frac{d + 2t_1}{d + t_1}, \quad C_2 = -\frac{2G}{E_c d t_1} \frac{d}{d + t_1},$$

$$C_3 = \frac{2G}{E_c d} \left[\frac{3d + 2t_1 + 2t_2}{(3d + 2t_1 + t_2)t_2} + \frac{d}{(d + t_1)t_1} \right]$$

With equation (14) and (15) the displacement can be solved out. By eliminating $u_1(x)$ we can get

$$u_1^{(4)}(x) - (C_1 + C_3)u_1^{(2)}(x) + C_1(C_2 + C_3)u_1(x) = 0 \quad (16)$$

The boundary conditions at the free end and the loading end are $u_1(0)=0$, $u_2(0)=0$, $T_1(l)=T_0$ and $T_2(l)=T_0$, which can be converted into conditions that only contain u_1 .

$$u_1(0) = 0, u_1'(l) = \frac{T_0}{EA}, u_1''(0) = 0, \quad (17)$$

$$u_1'''(l) = 0$$

With equation (16) and (17), $u_1(x)$ can be calculated by mathematical software. Then the shear stress distribution can be gained.

4 Finite Element Analysis

Finite element method is used to investigate stress distribution in CFRP rod bonding anchor and to test the accuracy of the theoretical model. The anchor was modeled by ANSYS solid 45 element, and nodes on the interface are merged since slippage is not considered.

4.1 Single Rod

Two types of anchor were modeled as shown in Figure 7. One contains bonding adhesive with constant modulus along full length, while the other contains 3 segments of adhesive with elastic modulus that gradually reduces from free end to loading end.

Figure 7 Numerical model of single rod
Material properties of CFRP and steel are presented in Table 1. The length of the anchor is 300mm, and diameter of CFRP rod is 5mm. The thickness of the steel barrel is 2.5mm. As for the first type, 3 kinds of parameter combination are selected. The elastic modulus and thickness of adhesive is respectively 5GPa and 2mm, 5GPa and 5mm, 2GPa and 5mm. For the second type with gradient modulus distribution, the elastic modulus of adhesive are respectively 11.6GPa, 0.5GPa and 0.15GPa from free end to loading end. Thus there are totally 4 numerical cases as shown in Table 2.

Table 1 Material properties (GPa)

Material	CFRP rod	Steel
E_x	181	200
E_y	10.05	/
E_z	10.05	/
ν_{xy}	0.28	0.27
ν_{yz}	0.3	/
ν_{xz}	0.28	/
G_{xy}	7.17	78.74
G_{yz}	7.17	/
G_{xz}	7.17	/

Table 2 Numerical cases of single rod anchor

No.	Modulus of adhesive (GPa)	Thickness of adhesive (mm)
1	5	2
2	5	5
3	2	5

No.	Modulus of adhesive (GPa)	Thickness of adhesive (mm)
4	11.6/0.5/0.15	5

In the FE model, tensile stress of 1500MPa is applied to the loading end of the CFRP rod, and end face of the barrel is fixed. The displacement and shear stress distribution of the rod can be gained from numerical results. In order to compare numerical results with theoretical ones, the parameters in each case are analyzed by theory in Section 3.1. Figure 8 and Figure 9 displays the displacement and shear stress distribution of CFRP rod in axial direction by theory and finite element method. Solid line represents for finite element results while dotted line represents for theoretical results. It can be seen that displacement and stress distribution results generally agree well, while there is some deviation between theoretical and numerical results of shear stress value at the loading end in Figure 9, which may be caused by stress discontinuity and approximation error in the theory.

Figure 8 Displacement distribution on single rod

Figure 9 Shear stress distribution on single rod

From Figure 8 we can notice that the stiffness of the single rod anchor increases as the modulus of the

adhesive increases or the thickness of the adhesive decreases. Figure 9 also shows that the peak value of shear stress increases as the modulus of the adhesive increases or the thickness of the adhesive decreases. When using gradient adhesives, the peak value reduces significantly at the loading end. Three peak values at each end of the adhesive segment can be roughly equal to each other by adjusting modulus value of adhesive, thus the whole anchorage length can be fully used. Therefore, the concentration of shear stress will be reduced and anchorage efficiency will be improved by using gradient modulus adhesive in bonding anchor.

4.2 Seven Rods

Side view of 7 rods anchor model is shown in Figure 10. The rods have a plum-shaped distribution in adhesive within certain spacing. Material properties of CFRP and steel are the same as above. Elastic modulus of adhesive is set as 5GPa. The length of the anchor is still 300mm, and diameter of CFRP rod is 5mm. Outside diameter of the anchor is 45mm with the barrel 5mm thick.

Figure 10 Numerical model of 7 rods

2 kinds of parameter combination are selected as shown in Table 3. The thickness of adhesive layer 1 and layer 2 is respectively 5mm+5mm and 8mm+2mm while outside diameter of anchor remains constant.

Table 3 Numerical cases of 7 rods anchor

No.	Thickness of adhesive layer 1	Thickness of adhesive layer 2
1	5	5
2	8	2

Tensile stress is still set as 1500MPa on each rod and constraints are the same as single rod anchor model. Axial displacement, Shear stress on the surface of center rod, inner and outer surface of side rods are obtained from finite element analysis. In

theoretical analysis, Mathematica 6.0 is used to solve the differential equation. For each case, the displacement distribution gained by theory and finite element method is shown in Figure 11 and Figure 12, while shear stress distribution is shown in Figure 13 and Figure 14.

Figure 11 Displacement distribution on 7 rods anchor ($t_1=5\text{mm}$, $t_2=5\text{mm}$)

Figure 12 Displacement distribution on 7 rods anchor ($t_1=8\text{mm}$, $t_2=2\text{mm}$)

Figure 13 Shear stress distribution on 7 rods anchor ($t_1=5\text{mm}$, $t_2=5\text{mm}$)

Figure 14 Shear stress distribution on 7 rods anchor ($t_1=8\text{mm}$, $t_2=2\text{mm}$)

As can be seen, the rod in the center has a shear stress peak with a relatively low value at the loading end, while the 6 rods on the side has a complex shear stress distribution. Shear stress in different positions in the same section of side rods may have an opposite direction, which is negative inside the rod while positive outside the rod. The peak value is also much bigger than that of center rod.

The theoretical and finite element results are generally the same except for some local positions. Some deviation is witnessed at the peak point of shear stress which has been explained in Section 4.1. In finite element analysis, direction of shear stress on inner surface of side rods has changed which does not agree with theoretical results in Figure 13 and 14. In a real situation, flexural deformation exists in side rods because of asymmetric stress state, and stress concentration at the loading end makes it more complicated to investigate the stress state in this area, so that the theoretical results may not be accurate here. In addition, as the space between center rod and side rods increases in condition of constant outside diameter, the stiffness of the anchor slightly increases while the shear stress peak value also increases.

5 Conclusions

With fundamental assumptions of elasticity and non-slip, a theoretical model of single rod and 7 rods bonding anchor is proposed on calculating shear stress distribution on the rods. The theoretical equations are derived from equilibrium and geometric conditions of CFRP rods and adhesive, and it is suitable for preliminary shear stress analysis in elastic state.

Finite element results show good agreement with theoretical results, thus the accuracy of the theory is confirmed. For single rod bonding anchor, as the modulus of the adhesive increases or the thickness of the adhesive decreases, stiffness of the single rod and peak value of shear stress will increase. As for 7 rods anchor, stiffness and shear stress peak value will also increase as the space between center rod and side rods increases. It can be concluded that parallel rods, especially the side rods have a complex stress state under tensile force, which may lead to premature failure in one of the rods.

Gradient modulus distribution of adhesive is proved to be an efficient way to reduce shear stress concentration and improve anchorage efficiency, but the actual operation still needs to be investigated and discussed.

References

- [1] Nanni, A., Bakis, C.E., O'Neil, P.E., and Dixon, T.O. Performance of FRP Tendon-Anchorage Systems for Prestressed Concrete Structures. *PCI Journal*, 1996, 41(1)34-43.
- [2] Ezzeldin Y., Sayed-Ahmed, Nigel G. Shrive. A new steel anchorage system for post-tensioning applications using carbon fibre reinforced plastic tendons. *Canadian journal of civil engineering*, 1998
- [3] Campbell, T.I., Shrive, N.G., Soudki, K.A., Al-Mayah, A., Keatley, J.P., Reda, M.M. Design and evaluation of a wedge-type anchor for fibre reinforced polymer tendons. *Canadian journal of civil engineering*, 2000, 27(5), p 985-992
- [4] Al-Mayah, A., Soudki, K.A., Plumtree, A. Experimental and analytical investigation of a stainless steel anchorage for CFRP prestressing tendons. *PCI Journal*, 2001, 46(2), p 88-100,
- [5] Al-Mayah, A., Soudki, K.A., Plumtree, A. Effect of sandblasting on interfacial contact behavior of carbon-fiber-reinforced polymer-metal couples. *Journal of Composites for Construction*, 2005, 9(4), p 289-295,
- [6] Al-Mayah, A., Soudki, K.A., Plumtree, A. Effect of sleeve material on interfacial contact behavior of CFRP-metal couples. *Journal of Materials in Civil Engineering*. 2006, 18(6), p 825-830
- [7] Al-Mayah, A., Soudki, K., Plumtree, A. Novel Anchor System for CFRP Rod: Finite-Element and Mathematical Models. *Journal of Composites for Construction*, 2007, 11(5), p 469-476
- [8] Jung, W.T., Park, J.S. An experimental study on tensile characteristic for CFRP cable without surface treatments. *Procedia Engineering*, 2011, 14, p 1518-1523
- [9] Benmokrane, Brahim, Zhang, Burong, Chennouf, Adil. Tensile properties and pullout behaviour of AFRP and CFRP rods for grouted anchor applications. *Construction and Building Materials*, 2000, 14(3), p 157-170
- [10] Zhang, Burong, Benmokrane, Brahim. Pullout bond properties of fiber-reinforced polymer tendons to grout. *Journal of Materials in Civil Engineering*, 2002, 14(5), p 399-408
- [11] Tsyuyoshi Enomoto, Kenichi Ushijima. Use of CFCC Tendons and Reinforcements in Concrete Structures for Durability. *APFIS*, 2012
- [12] Rohleder Jr., W. Jay, Tang, Benjamin, Doe, Thomas A., Grace, Nabil F., Burgess, Christopher J. CFRP Strand Application on Penobscot Narrows Cable Stayer Bridge. *Transportation Research Record*, 2008, p 169-176
- [13] Zhang, Burong, Benmokrane, Brahim, Chennouf, Adil. Prediction of Tensile Capacity of Bond Anchorages for FRP Tendons. *Journal of Composites for Construction*, 2000, 4(2), p 39-47
- [14] Urs Meier. Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer Cables: Why? Why Not? What If?. 11th Arab Structural Engineering Conference (ASEC), 2009
- [15] MEI Kui-hua. Analysis of Mechanical Behavior of CFRP Cable Bonding Anchors. *Bridge Construction*, 2007, 3, p80-83